

Definition, Structure and Core Functions of the State Image

Rosa Nurtazina, Yerkebulan Zhumashov, Maral Tomanova

Abstract—Humanity is entering an era when "virtual reality" as the image of the world created by the media with the help of the Internet does not match the reality in many respects, when new communication technologies create a fundamentally different and previously unknown "global space". According to these technologies, the state begins to change the basic technology of political communication of the state and society, the state and the state. Nowadays image of the state becomes the most important tool and technology.

Image is a purposefully created image granting political object (person, organization, country, etc.) certain social and political values and promoting more emotional perception.

Political image of the state plays an important role in international relations. The success of the country's foreign policy, development of trade and economic relations with other countries depends on whether it is positive or negative. Foreign policy image has an impact on political processes taking place in the state: the negative image of the country's can be used by opposition forces as one of the arguments to criticize the government and its policies.

Keywords—Image of the country, country's image classification, function of the country image, country's image components.

I. INTRODUCTION

INDIVIDUAL such as political leader of the country and the country itself (or separate spheres of public life: political power, economy, military, foreign policy, etc.) both can be image objects. One of the most famous definitions of the country image is the definition proposed by the World Tourism Organization according to which the country's image is a set of emotional and traditional perceptions arising from the comparison of all country's features, its own experience and rumors affecting the creation of a certain image [1].

Recently, definition of political and geographical image proposed by D. Zamyatin became widespread regarded as a "compaction and concentration of leading characters, symbols and features of individual countries, regions or political and military alliances in political terms [2]. This image includes a number of simplified notions which may be expressed as "bright and sometimes primitive slogans".

The face of the country is highly depending on its image. Both foreign investors and public opinion of other countries respond to it, having a direct impact on their leaders. Similar characteristics are inherent for the image of the leader. A leader's rating is a measure of how actively the population perceives his reforms and what will be the level of confidence

R. N. Gumilev, Y. Zh. Gumilev, and M. T. Gumilev are with the Eurasian National University, Mirzoyan Str., 2, Astana, Republic of Kazakhstan, 010008 (e-mail: roza_nur@mail.ru, erkezhumashov@mail.ru, maral-kz@list.ru).

in his actions. As national security basically comprises stability, image aspects cannot be left aside.

Contemporary world as a world of information gives importance to the verbal model of the world. Representativeness of the country and its leaders in this verbal model affects significantly the characteristics of the real world.

An example of attention to the country's image can be German competition "How to promote Germany" launched in 1995. The project was sponsored by the major German companies such as Lufthansa, BMW, Siemens, Bosch. As a result, one hundred of the best works were to make an album "One hundred ways to promote Germany". Participants had to think on the following questions: What is the place of Germany in the global economy? What is its role in the development of other countries? What is its role in the unification of Europe? What is the image of Germany and how to determine it? [3].

S. Black gives an example of "Visit Malaysia" [4], which aims to increase the number of tourists. The program comprised video production, media relations at the international level, sponsorship in cooperation with companies such as Coca-Cola, inviting journalists to the country for study visits.

One important issue that arises while analyzing the image of the state is conformity or nonconformity of proclaimed, expected and real image of the state. One of the most prominent experts in the field of PR H. Levinson [5] suggests the following questions to determine it:

- What decisions do the leaders of the country take, based on the assessment of state's economy, social policy, foreign policy and plans for the future?
- How do the leaders of the country explain their actions in communication with citizens (convince, persuade, attract, etc.)?
- What kind of the country do citizens want to see? How do the leaders see the image of the country? How does the foreign audience see the image of the country?
- According to Ye. Galumova [6], the most important way to find out what do different social groups of the country think, is the scientific research implying asking respondents several informal questions:
- If the state has a clear image, whether its leaders and citizens act in accordance with it? Perhaps they say one thing and do another?
- If the country has a clear image, whether its citizens can live and act in accordance with it? Or excessive social demands for members of society, low standards of living

and other factors make it impossible?

- In case of need to change the image of the country whether ordinary citizens contribute it by taking part in the government?
- If the state does not have a clear image, does it cause concerns, limited identification or discrepancies of ratings?

In the structure of the political image of the country it is possible to distinguish two components and each includes a number of images:

1. Foreign political component of the image, i.e. idea of the country, formed by foreign audiences and world community;
2. Internal political component of the image, i.e. idea of the country, formed by citizens of this state;

Image of the state shows its economic strength, power, wealth and level of culture. It is an indicator of state's credibility and success of the actions in the international arena. Image of the state is directly related to the attitude of the foreign public and its own citizens. Thus, due to the fact that image of a country is a rather multi-dimensional category there are different approaches to the classification of the image in various sources.

For example, some researchers identify an objective image, or real image which is impression of the country formed by internal or foreign public; others identify subjective image which is idea of the country's leader and his entourage on how the image is perceived by citizens, or idea of citizens on how their country is seen abroad; others identify modeled image which is the image that leader team of the country or image makers try to create.

The state has several objective images: economic, social, humanitarian, political, cultural, environmental, etc.; each can be both positive and negative. They can be modified both according to the situation and because of the efforts of image makers' team. The primary image of the country arises as a result of image formation, when initial expectations of citizens or foreign audiences are taken as a base.

The primary image of the country is a comprehensive picture of the country as a whole certain givenness (the subject of political, economic and other activities) which forms and fixes in public minds as a result of the initial contact. Also, the primary image includes basic characteristics of the ideal image but differs from the ideal for some features.

During the formation of the country's image in the public eye, it transforms consistently. Its basic features retain but new so-called "surface" features added which reflect new realities. The new image of the country can be designated as secondary.

Secondary image of the country occurs only during competition (political, economic, informational, etc.) with other countries.

The mass consciousness has a habit to compare different objects with certain human qualities. These qualities are transformed into a secondary image of the country. It should testify that the state is a friendly, caring, honest, giving the impression, etc. towards its citizens and other states. However, the difficulty is how to achieve the desired result and to make

sure that the created image is believed by various community groups within and outside the country.

Besides, political image of the state, as well as personal political image, can act as a "self-image" or "me-image" (the image of the state, existing in the minds of its people), perceived image (image formed in the minds of the peoples of other countries) and requested image (the image of the desired by the state for the most effective implementation of its policies).

On the basis of several studies the following sequence of image perception of the state can be distinguished:

- political and geographic image of the country is projected in the mass consciousness as a favorable political and geographical foothold, which would be base for other images;
- formed political and geographical image is covered with natural and resource image which is attractive and distinctive only for this country in the form of a colorful natural scenery;
- this natural and geographic portrait "civilized" through civilization-cultural image as a national cultural symbol comprised historical heritage of the country and recognized worldwide;
- socio-mental image of people as a positive character lies on the harmonious natural civilization and cultural background;
- positivity of socio-mental image is reinforced by the results of people's work in the form of production and economic image as a symbol of prosperity, power and influence capacity of the state;
- state's efforts in historical perspective shows as the image of national value, indicating the priority national of goal and the meaning of life.

Another approach can violate the logic of perception and can lead to a discrepancy of planned and obtained images. The positive image of the state should be held together by internal logic and consistency that gives the impression of a holistic image, consisting of six sides.

Further, when structuring the images of state, they can be divided into six types:

1. Political and geographical image as a seal and concentration of leading geographical characters and symbols of the country in political sense. In the mass consciousness political and geographical image identifies the state with some part of the world in a certain environment of states. Thus, the Soviet Union was presented as one-sixth of the land mass, Russia as Eastern Europe or Eurasia, United States as New World, European countries as Western Europe or the Old World, China as Celestial Empire, Switzerland as The Pearl of the Alps, Finland as Suomi, Italy as Apennines and etc.

2. Natural resources image as a seal and concentration of leading signs and symbols of national resource wealth in nature, landscape or climate. In the mass consciousness natural resources are identified the state with some inherent nature symbol. (Japan is the Land of the Rising Sun, South Korea is the Land of Morning Calm, Canada is a Maple Leaf Country, England is foggy Albion, Russia is a country of snow

and frost, the USA are the Wild West). The same expressive symbols of the country are different animals, which dominantly live in this country and traditionally used in the symbolism. For example, Russia is a country of bears, USA are known with white eagles, China is a country of giant panda, Australia is famous with koala, an elephant is a symbol for Africa, etc.

3. Civilizational and cultural image is a seal and concentration of national cultural signs, symbols and features of people in the country's historical and civilizational dimension. Civilizational and cultural image must be in harmony with political, geographical and natural resource images as it put a bright and recognizable light in the image of the country. Civilizational and cultural image is intended to identify people of the nation with its cultural and historical heritage of world significance. Cultural and historical symbol is desirable to be included in the register of the United Nations (cultural monuments of world civilization). For example, Russia Kremlin refers to such monuments; in the USA it is Statue of Liberty, China has the Great Wall, Pyramids in Egypt, Japanese hieroglyphs, Tower of Westminster Palace in England, Eiffel Tower in France, Colosseum in Italy, Acropolis in Greece, Buddhist pagoda in India, etc.

4. Social and mental image is a seal and concentration of leading social signs and symbols, features of people in the mental attitude. Socio-mental image identifies people with the most typical social and psychological characteristics. So, Germans are precise and accurate, Americans are businesslike, Japanese are polite and committed to traditions, French are impermanent, British are prim, Chinese are hardworking, Indians are mysterious, Arabs are restless, Russians are creative, Italians are romantic and etc. Due to the socio-mental image established in the minds of the world community, it is possible to find an area of activity in which this nation reaches the success. For example, Germans in science, Americans in business, Japanese in preserving the traditions, French in fashion, British in education, Chinese in the construction of huge structures, Russians in a theatrical and literary spheres, Italians in the fine arts, etc.).

5. Production and economic image is a seal and concentration of leading economic symbols, signs and the country's capacity in scientific, industrial, defense and other industrial relations. Production and economic image identifies the state with some economic niche in the global economic division. So, Japan is associated with high-intellectual video, audio and automotive equipment; USA - with dollar, "Coca-Cola" and "Pepsi" drinks, Hollywood, fast food restaurants, "Boeing" airplanes, "Microsoft" products, space shuttles, weapons, etc.; France with fashion, wine; Great Britain with seagoing vessels; Germany with automobiles, construction technologies, optics, etc.; Russia with space, small arms, aircraft, the Bolshoi Theatre.

6. National value image is a seal and concentration of leading signs and symbols expressing state interests, goals and aspirations in the national ideology. National evaluative image identifies the state and its people with its historical values offered to the world and defended consistently by the state.

Thus, for the USA it is freedom and independence, for Russia is justice and interests of all nations, for Europe is civility, for Asia is respect for the traditions, etc.

In the world consciousness the global image of the country is determined by material and spiritual values which it exports. Brzezinski wrote about this: "Rome exported laws, Great Britain exported parliamentary party democracy, France - culture and republican nationalism, and the contemporary United States - scientific and technological innovation and mass culture ..." [7].

The following components can be distinguished in the structure of the state image, although this list is certainly not comprehensive:

- Image of the power;
- Image of opposition, political parties and movements;
- Socio-economic image of the country (important for tourism, migration flows, etc.);
- Business image of the country (related to the concepts of competitiveness, to analyze which experts of the International Institute for Management Development use 288 estimated parameters, formed on the basis of statistical data and expert reports);
- Image of any government organization;
- Image of the armed forces of the state;
- Image of the capital of the state
- Image of goods produced in the country;
- Image of the history of the country;
- Image of the events occurring in the country at the moment;
- Cultural image of the state, i.e. ideas about the country's culture, citizens' attitude to the country, ideas about education, etc.
- Image of crime situation in the country can be also treated as a separate category.

The following characteristics and features of the country's image can be emphasized, based on a series of works devoted to the image:

- In comparison with the object, image is simplified, being a public portrait. However, image underlines the specificity and uniqueness of the object. In addition, image can be viewed as a kind of a folded message: a significant amount of information carried by the object through the image is reduced to a limited set of characters;
- Image is concrete but still movable and changeable; it stays in correction all the time, adapting to the demands of the current situation;
- Image idealizes object to a certain extent, exaggerating its best features, or giving it additional social, ideological, psychological qualities in accordance with the expectations of those who are aims of image advertising;
- Being closely tied to the prototype, the image still lives by its own laws in accordance with the psychological orientations of routine consciousness of the population;
- Image takes place between the actual and desired, between perception and imagination, enhancing the perception of the object artificially, but doing this in a

given direction, encouraging the imagination of the public and its "complicity" in shaping of the country's image.

D. Bourstin, summing up the common signs of image that really exist in practice, sees the basic requirements for the country's image the following way:

- The image of the state should be synthetic, planned to produce a certain impression through the signs (heraldic symbols).
- Image of the country should be believable, credible. Nobody needs the image if it is not trusted by the people. Image should be identified with a particular country. To be alive, it must meet the requirements of common sense.
- It must be passive. Society should conform to the image of the country to some extent also.
- Image of the country should be bright and concrete. It works better if appeals to the senses. It is quickly perceived when focuses on certain features and highlights brightly one or more of the most country-specific features.
- Image of the country should be simplified. To avoid undesirable effects, it should be more be simple than the object itself. The most simple and effective image is quickly memorable.
- Despite the concreteness, image of the country should be uncertain to some extent and hover somewhere between the senses and reason, between expectations and reality. The image must resist the unforeseen developments, changes in political preferences; meet wishes and expectations of different people [8].

The main functions of the country image include:

- Identification (we get the country information as quickly as possible). This communicative function facilitates perception of the information by the audience and informs about the positive aspects of life in the country, as the mass consciousness is ready to receive only the most crucial information specifying basic parameters than to treat the entire amount of information.
- Idealization. This function is designed to provide the most favored perception of a country's image by projecting the most preferred characteristics in the target audience.
- Opposition (based on the other images, images of other countries or on the history of the country). This feature focuses on preparing the base for the creation of a positive image of the country.
- In addition to clearly viewed communicative functions of country's image, Ye. Blazhnov notes other functions such as nominative, esthetic and address:
- Nominative - shows (highlights, rebuilds, differentiates) the state in the geopolitical situation and the environment of other states, and demonstrates the distinctive features.
- Esthetic - is designed to elevate the impression made on the public by the country.
- Address - implies that there is a connection between the image of the country and the target audience for which the image is intended, and that it responds to the needs of the audience [9].

REFERENCES

- [1] A.P. Pankruxin, *Marketing Territorij*. Moscow, 2002.
- [2] D.N.Zamyatin, "Geopolitika obraza i strukturirovanie metaprostranstva," *Polis*. 2003, vol, 1. s. 83.
- [3] "Reklamnyj mir". 1995, Vol, 17.
- [4] S. Black, *The essentials of public relations*. London, 1993. P.70.
- [5] H. Levinson, "How to Undermine an Organization," *PR Journal*.1996.
- [6] E.A. Galumov, *Mezhdunarodnyj Imidzh Rossii*. Moscow, 2003.
- [7] Z. Bzhezinskij, *Vybor. mirovoe gospodstvo ili globalnoe liderstvo*. Moscow, 2004.
- [8] D. Burstin, *Imidzh*. p. 291.
- [9] E.A. Blazhnov, *Pablik Rilejshenz*. Moscow, 1994. p. 405.